

Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Online Training on the Recommendation Intention of Port Employees in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

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This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of online training on the recommendation intention of port employees in Indonesia. The research employed a quantitative approach using a survey method. The population consisted of 181 employees who had participated in online training programs, and saturated sampling was applied, involving the entire population as respondents. Data were collected through a Likert-scale questionnaire (1–5) and analyzed using SPSS version 29. The analysis included validity and reliability tests, classical assumption tests, multiple linear regression, t-test, and F-test. The results indicate that perceptions of training components simultaneously have a significant effect on recommendation intention (F-test, $p < 0.05$). However, the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.131$) shows that these variables explain only 13.1% of the variance in recommendation intention. Partially, perceived trainer quality has a significant positive effect, while perceived benefits show a significant negative effect. Perceptions of training materials and facilities do not significantly influence recommendation intention. These findings highlight the crucial role of trainer competence in shaping employees' willingness to recommend online training programs. The study suggests that training providers should focus on improving trainer quality and managing participants' expectations regarding training benefits. Future research is recommended to incorporate additional variables such as satisfaction, loyalty, and organizational support to develop a more comprehensive predictive model.

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Introduction

The rapid digital transformation in the logistics and port sector has significantly reshaped operational systems, communication flows, and human resource (HR) management practices in Indonesia. Ports play a strategic role in supporting national economic growth, facilitating trade, and ensuring the smooth movement of goods across regions. In this increasingly competitive and technology-driven environment, organizational sustainability depends not only on infrastructure and capital investment but also on the quality and adaptability of human resources. Human resources are widely recognized as a critical determinant of organizational performance because they directly influence planning, execution, service quality, and strategic decision-making processes.

Effective human resource management contributes substantially to organizational productivity and competitiveness. Previous studies emphasize that employee competence, motivation, and continuous professional development are central to achieving sustainable organizational performance. Training programs, as part of HR development initiatives, aim to enhance employees' knowledge, skills, and attitudes

to meet evolving job demands. In service-intensive sectors such as port operations, employee capability is particularly crucial due to the need for coordination, safety compliance, digital system integration, and customer-oriented service delivery.

The emergence of online or digital training has become a strategic solution for organizations facing geographical dispersion, time constraints, and cost-efficiency demands. Indonesia, as an archipelagic country with port employees spread across various regions, presents unique challenges in delivering conventional face-to-face training. Online training enables organizations to provide standardized learning materials, reach employees in remote locations, and ensure continuity of learning without disrupting operational schedules. Furthermore, digital learning platforms allow flexible access, interactive content, and scalable training management systems.

Despite its strategic advantages, the effectiveness of online training remains a critical concern. Organizations must ensure that digital training programs not only deliver content but also generate meaningful learning outcomes and behavioral changes. Training effectiveness is often evaluated through participant satisfaction, knowledge acquisition, skill improvement, and performance enhancement. One of the most widely used frameworks in training evaluation is the Kirkpatrick Model, which assesses training outcomes across four levels: reaction, learning, behavior, and results. The reaction level, which focuses on participants' perceptions and satisfaction, serves as the initial indicator of training success and may influence subsequent behavioral intentions.

In the context of online training, participants' perceptions regarding training materials, perceived benefits, trainer competence, and supporting facilities play an important role in shaping their overall evaluation of the program. Positive perceptions may lead to stronger engagement, improved learning experience, and favorable post-training attitudes. One important behavioral outcome associated with training evaluation is recommendation intention—the willingness of participants to recommend the training program to colleagues. Recommendation intention reflects a form of positive word-of-mouth behavior, which indicates perceived value and satisfaction with the training experience.

Although previous research has examined the relationship between training quality and employee performance, relatively limited studies have focused specifically on recommendation intention as an outcome variable in online training contexts, particularly within the port sector in Indonesia. Existing studies often emphasize digital readiness, organizational performance, or competency development, without conducting structured empirical evaluation of online training components. Moreover, research conducted in other sectors suggests that e-learning design, trainer quality, and perceived usefulness significantly influence learning outcomes and satisfaction. However, empirical evidence regarding how these factors shape employees' intention to recommend online training programs in port organizations remains insufficient.

The port sector has distinctive characteristics compared to other industries. It involves complex coordination between operational units, regulatory compliance, safety standards, and technological integration. Therefore, training programs must address both technical competencies and soft skills, including leadership, communication, and problem-solving abilities. Evaluating the effectiveness of online training in this sector is essential to ensure that HR development strategies align with organizational goals and operational demands.

Furthermore, recommendation intention can serve as an indirect indicator of perceived training value and organizational learning culture. When employees are willing to recommend training programs, it suggests that they perceive the program as beneficial, relevant, and professionally delivered. Conversely, low recommendation intention may signal gaps in training design, delivery methods, or post-training impact. Understanding the determinants of recommendation intention can therefore help organizations refine training strategies and allocate resources more effectively.

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of online training on the recommendation intention of port employees in Indonesia. Specifically, it examines how perceptions of training materials, perceived benefits, trainer competence, and supporting facilities influence employees' willingness to recommend the training program. By adopting a quantitative approach and analyzing responses from 181 employees across various regions and job positions, this study provides empirical evidence regarding the relationship between training evaluation components and behavioral intention outcomes.

The research contributes to literature in several ways. First, it extends the application of training evaluation frameworks to the port sector, which has received limited scholarly attention. Second, it

integrates multiple perceptual dimensions of training quality to analyze their collective and partial influence on recommendation intention. Third, it offers practical insights for HR managers and training providers in designing more effective online training programs tailored to geographically dispersed workforces.

In addition to its theoretical contribution, this study has important managerial implications. By identifying which training components significantly influence recommendation intention, organizations can prioritize improvements in trainer competence, content relevance, or technological support systems. This evidence-based evaluation approach supports data-driven HR decision-making and strengthens the alignment between digital transformation strategies and workforce development initiatives.

As digital transformation continues to redefine the logistics and port industry, evaluating the effectiveness of online training becomes increasingly crucial. Understanding employees' perceptions and behavioral responses provides valuable insights into how training programs can be optimized to enhance organizational performance and sustain competitive advantage. This study seeks to fill the existing research gap by empirically examining the determinants of recommendation intention in the context of online training among port employees in Indonesia.

Method

This study was conducted on port employees in Indonesia who had participated in online (digital) training, using a descriptive (Mulyadi, 2011; Sugiyono, 2018) and inferential quantitative approach with a survey method through a questionnaire. Data was obtained online through a structured questionnaire.

The population consisted of all employees who had participated in the training, with a total sample of 181 training participants, comprising 46 women and 135 men. Data processing used descriptive statistical methods, including frequency and percentage for demographic data, as well as mean and standard deviation for each indicator.

The validity test was conducted using the product-moment correlation test ($r\text{-count} > r\text{-table}$), while reliability was measured using the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient ($\alpha > 0.7$). Classical assumption tests for regression analysis included tests of normality, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, and linearity.

Data analysis was carried out using SPSS version 29 with inferential analysis, including the One-Way ANOVA test, independent t-test, and Multiple Linear Regression Analysis to identify dominant influencing factors.

Managerial implications were analyzed using Kirkpatrick's Model theory (1994) (Gouvany et al., 2024; Inayah Zainuddin et al., 2024; Nurjaman et al., 2020; Review et al., 2021), which consists of four levels: reaction, learning, behavior, and results, as the conceptual basis. This study focuses on the reaction level (participant satisfaction) as an initial predictor of training success.

Results and Discussion

The distribution of questionnaires and data collection was carried out for 1 (one) year, starting from January 6, 2025 to December 29, 2025, carried out *online* through the learning system provided for port employee training, with a total distribution of 200 respondents and 181 respondents returned. The questionnaire distribution was limited to Port employees in Indonesia, who had developed their soft skills through online training. The HR division team provided learning systems and facilities with various training titles covering 7 (seven) themes, consisting of Financial & Life Planning Literacy (Eupeña et al., 2025), Communication (Paramita & Adawiyah, 2021), Brand (Hermanto et al., 2022) & Reputation (Robbani & Adawiyah, 2023; Suryani & El Adawiyah, 2025), Sustainable & Responsible Business (Diyah et al., 2022), Entrepreneurship & Innovation (El Adawiyah et al., 2021; Fitrio et al., 2019; Hadiwardoyo, 2020), Organization & Human Capital Development (Brymer et al., 2014; Endri, 2010; Sugiyanto & Marka, 2017), Leadership (Sinaga et al., 2023) & Management (Tuti & Adawiyah, 2020), Port Operations & Technology (Sanjaya et al., 2025; Sari et al., n.d.; Schauffel et al., 2021).

Respondent Description

This section describes the characteristics of the respondents who completed the questionnaire. The respondent data described includes gender, position, and location of the training employees, as seen in Figures 1, 2, and 3.

Figure 1. Gender

Figure 2. Participant Position

Figure 3. Employee Location

Figure 1 shows that the most dominant respondents were men, with 135 people or 75%, and women, 46 people or 25%. Figure 2 shows the positions of port employees who have participated in online training, including 5 Directors, 5 Deputy Directors, 1 Director's Secretary, 4 Auditors, 26 Managers, 10 Assistant Managers, 10 Supervisors, 49 Senior Officers, and 71 Staff Officers. and in Figure 3, the locations of employees who have undertaken online training from various regions in Indonesia include Jakarta 21 people, Sulawesi 9 people, Makassar Strait 7 people, Ambon 7 people, Surabaya 13 people, Jambi 7 people, Dumai 7 people, Banten 12 people, East Kalimantan 8 people, Pontianak 11 people, Cirebon 8 people, Palembang 7 people, Medan 7 people, Makassar 7 people, Bitung 7 people, Batang City, 7 people, Banyuwangi Regency 7 people, Gresik 7 people, Batu Bara Regency 7 people, Tolitoli 7 people, and Bali 8 people.

Pretest

A *pretest* was conducted on 30 respondents, with validity and reliability tests to verify the feasibility of the questionnaire used in the study. The data were declared valid. The validity test in this study used factor analysis, based on the *factor loading component matrix* and the *Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure (KMO)* (Hair et al., 2010). An indicator is considered valid if it has a value greater than 0.5, while the reliability of a questionnaire is assessed based on the value of Cronbach's Alpha. A questionnaire is said to have reliability if the Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than 0.6 (see Appendix 1 for results).

Validity Test

The validity test in this study used the SPSS 29 application with the CFA (*Confirmatory Factor Analysis*) method or factor analysis by looking at the results of *the rotated component matrix varimax*. The output is as follows.

Table 1. Validity Test Results

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0,929
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6785,166
	df	190
	Sig.	0,000

The KMO value obtained was 0.929. Based on Kaiser's (1974) criteria, this value is in the "Very Good" category ($KMO \geq 0.90$), which indicates that the sample used is very adequate and the data is suitable for factor analysis. The results of the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity showed a Chi-Square value of 6785.166 with 190 degrees of freedom (df) and reached a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). This result is statistically significant, meaning that there is sufficient correlation between variables in the correlation matrix. In other words, the data meets the requirements to proceed to factor analysis.

Table 2. Rotated Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
MATERI1	.958	.088
MANFAAT3	.957	.101
TRAINER1	.952	.113
TRAINER5	.951	.063
TRAINER2	.942	.115
TRAINER4	.936	.115
MANFAAT1	.934	.126
MATERI4	.931	.089
TRAINER3	.928	.102
MATERI2	.927	.128
REKOMENDASI1	.923	.074
REKOMENDASI2	.923	.107
MATERI3	.914	.101
MANFAAT2	.903	.144
FASILITAS4	.124	.951
FASILITAS1	.073	.948
FASILITAS3	.078	.946
FASILITAS2	.105	.943
SARANA2	.138	.924
SARANA1	.112	.908

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
a Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Based on the results of the Rotated Component Matrix analysis using the Varimax Rotation method, it can be concluded that the 20 research instrument items were successfully grouped into two main components or dimensions with a very clear structure. This grouping indicates that the measured construction consists of two separate and meaningful factors, namely:

1) Component 1

The first component contains 13 items consisting of aspects related to Material, Benefits, Trainer, and Recommendations. All items in this component have very high factor loadings (all above 0.90), indicating a very strong correlation between these items and this component. The items with the highest loadings are material1 (0.958), benefits3 (0.957), and trainer1 (0.952). Component Interpretation: Based on the items that make it up, Component 1 can be identified as a factor that represents "Quality of

Training Content and Instructors." This component captures participants' perceptions regarding the quality of the material delivered, the benefits obtained, and the trainer's competence and performance.

2) Component 2

The second component contains 7 items, all of which come from the Facilities and Supporting Facilities aspect. Similar to Component 1, all items in this component also have very high factor loadings (all above 0.90). The items with the highest loadings are facility4 (0.951), facility1 (0.948), and facility3 (0.946). Component Interpretation: Based on its constituent items, Component 2 can be identified as a factor representing "Quality of Facilities and Supporting Facilities". This component measures participants' assessment of the completeness and quality of the physical facilities and infrastructure provided during the training.

Reliability Test

A reliability test is a value that indicates the consistency with which respondents answer questions in a questionnaire. Its purpose is to measure whether the questions in the questionnaire are suitable for research purposes. The results of the reliability test for the research sample data used Cronbach's method to meet the data reliability criteria.

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0,965	20

The Cronbach's Alpha value obtained was 0.965 for 20 questions/statements. Based on reliability criteria (e.g., George & Mallery, 2003), this value is in the "Very Good" category ($\alpha \geq 0.90$). This indicates that the research instrument has very high internal consistency and is highly reliable. In other words, all items measure the same construct consistently and reliably.

Descriptive Statistics of Variables

The descriptive statistical results of the average respondents are shown in the table below:

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
MATERI1	181	2,00	4,00	3,6464	0,49086
MATERI2	181	3,00	4,00	3,6519	0,47768
MATERI3	181	2,00	4,00	3,6133	0,49960
MATERI4	181	2,00	4,00	3,6630	0,48558
MANFAAT1	181	2,00	4,00	3,6630	0,48558
MANFAAT2	181	2,00	4,00	3,6685	0,48368
MANFAAT3	181	2,00	4,00	3,6464	0,50205
TRAINER1	181	2,00	4,00	3,6796	0,47967
TRAINER2	181	2,00	4,00	3,6630	0,48558
TRAINER3	181	3,00	4,00	3,6354	0,48266
TRAINER4	181	2,00	4,00	3,6354	0,49404
TRAINER5	181	3,00	4,00	3,6630	0,47400
FASILITAS1	181	3,00	4,00	3,7072	0,45632
FASILITAS2	181	3,00	4,00	3,7238	0,44838
FASILITAS3	181	3,00	4,00	3,7293	0,44556
FASILITAS4	181	3,00	4,00	3,7127	0,45375
SARANA1	181	3,00	4,00	3,7017	0,45880
SARANA2	181	3,00	4,00	3,7072	0,45632
REKOMENDASI1	181	2,00	4,00	3,6243	0,52943
REKOMENDASI2	181	2,00	4,00	3,6851	0,47755

Descriptively, it can be concluded that: The level of satisfaction or positive perception of respondents towards all aspects of training/research instruments is Very High, indicated by the mean value of all items approaching the maximum score (4.00). The responses of 181 respondents are very homogeneous and consistent, indicated by the low standard deviation for all items. The Facilities & Means dimension received the highest average rating, followed closely by the Content & Instructor Quality Dimension.

Multicollinearity Test

The results of the multicollinearity test in this study using SPSS version 29, each independent variable with the dependent variable, namely the independent variable perception of training material (X1), Perception of benefits (X2), Perception of Trainer (X3) Perception of Facilities (X4), Perception of Facilities (X5), against the dependent variable Recommendation Intention (Y1).

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test

Variabel Independen	Tolerance	VIF	Keterangan
MATERI	0,797	1,254	Tidak ada multikolinearitas
MANFAAT	0,113	8,869	Tidak ada multikolinearitas
TRAINER	0,11	9,115	Tidak ada multikolinearitas
FASILITAS	0,224	4,472	Tidak ada multikolinearitas
SARANA	0,219	4,562	Tidak ada multikolinearitas

Based on the multicollinearity test results, it can be concluded that the regression model is suitable for further analysis because there are no serious multicollinearity issues. All VIF values are below 10 and the Tolerance value is above 0.10, thus meeting the non-multicollinearity assumption in linear regression analysis.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study using SPSS version 29, each independent variable with the dependent variable, namely the independent variable perception of training material (X1), Perception of benefits (X2), Perception of Trainer (X3) Perception of Facilities (X4), Perception of Facilities (X5), against the dependent variable Recommendation Intention (Y1):

Figure 4. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

From the scatterplot image above, it can be observed that the points are spread randomly and do not form a specific pattern. The points are spread both above and below the number 0 on the Y-axis. This indicates that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model. Thus, H0 is accepted, which means that the regression model meets the heteroscedasticity assumption or has a constant residual variance (homoscedasticity). The conclusion from this heteroscedasticity test is that the regression model used in this study is suitable for use because it does not violate the heteroscedasticity assumption. In other words, the estimated results of the regression model are BLUE (Best *Linear Unbiased Estimator*), so they can be relied upon for prediction and inference.

Normality Test

Based on the normal p-plot graph using SPSS version 29, each independent variable with the dependent variable, namely the independent variable of perception of training material (X1), Perception of benefits (X2), Perception of Trainer (X3), Perception of Facilities (X4), Perception of Facilities (X5), against the dependent variable of Recommendation Intention (Y1):

Figure 5. Normality Test Results

Based on the resulting Normal PP Plot graph, it can be observed that the plot points between the independent variables (Perception of Training Material/X1, Perception of Benefits/X2, Perception of Trainer/X3, Perception of Facilities/X4, and Perception of Facilities/X5) with the dependent variable (Intention to Recommendation/Y1) are spread and follow the diagonal line. The distribution pattern of points approaching the diagonal line indicates that the residual data is close to a normal distribution. The visual results of the graph indicate that there are no significant deviations from the normality assumption. Thus, it can be concluded that the data of this study meets the normality assumption and is worthy of being continued to the next stage of analysis.

Hypothesis Testing

This research has passed validity and reliability tests. Furthermore, multiple linear regression was used to test the research hypothesis. This aims to determine the influence of training material perception, benefits perception, trainer perception, facilities perception, and facilities perception on recommendation intention. The coefficient of determination test in this study used SPSS 29, with the following table output.

Table 6. Results of the Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary					
Dependen Variabel	Independen Variabel	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
Niat Rekomendasi	Persepsi Materi Pelatihan, Persepsi Manfaat, Persepsi Trainer, Persepsi Fasilitas, dan Persepsi Sarana	.362 ^a	0,131	0,106	7,19353

a. Predictors: (Constant), SARANA, MATERI, MANFAAT, FASILITAS, TRAINER

Based on table 6. The results of the Determination Coefficient Test above can be interpreted as follows: The R value (Multiple Correlation Coefficient) of 0.362 indicates that the relationship between the five independent variables together with the dependent variable (Recommendation Intention) is in the weak to moderate category. The positive direction of the relationship indicates that an increase in perceptions of material, benefits, trainers, facilities, and means tends to be followed by an increase in recommendation intentions. The R Square value (Coefficient of Determination) of 0.131 means that the independent variables (Perception of Training Material, Perception of Benefits, Perception of Trainers, Perception of Facilities, and Perception of Facilities) together are able to explain 13.1% of the variation in the

Recommendation Intention variable. The remaining 86.9% is explained by other factors not included in this research model. The Adjusted R Square of 0.106 is a determination coefficient that has been adjusted for the number of independent variables and sample size. This value is lower than the R Square, which is a reasonable condition in multiple regression analysis. The positive Adjusted R Square indicates that, despite the non-dominant contribution of the independent variables, the model still has statistically significant predictive power. The Standard Error of the Estimate of 7.19353 indicates the average deviation between the model's predicted value and the actual value. The smaller this value, the more accurate the model's predictions. This value can be used as a reference in evaluating the model's prediction error level.

The coefficient of determination results showing an R Square value of 0.131 imply that although the five perception factors (material, benefits, trainer, facilities, and infrastructure) influence recommendation intentions, their contribution is relatively limited. This indicates that there are other, more dominant factors outside of these five variables that influence training participants' recommendation intentions, such as loyalty factors, previous experience, social environment, or the overall quality of the training. This finding is in line with several previous studies stating that perceptions of training components do influence recommendation intentions but are not the sole determinant. Therefore, in developing strategies to increase recommendation intentions, it is necessary to also consider other variables that may have a stronger influence. Although the contribution of the independent variables is not large, this regression model still has statistical significance (shown through the F test which will be discussed in the next section) and can be used as a basis for identifying aspects of perception that need to be improved. The practical implication is that training organizers can focus on improving the quality of the material, perceived benefits, trainer competence, and facilities and supporting tools, although it is recognized that these efforts need to be complemented by interventions on other factors outside the model. The hypotheses tested in the F test are as follows: **H₀**: There is no significant simultaneous influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. **H₁**: There is a significant simultaneous influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The test was conducted using a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The decision was taken by comparing the **Sig. value** with α : If **Sig.** < **0.05**, then H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted. If **Sig.** ≥ **0.05**, then H₀ fails to be rejected.

The results of data processing with SPSS version 29 obtained the following ANOVA output.

Table 7. F Test Results

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Niat Rekomendasi	Regression	1366,543	5	273,309	5,282	<.001 ^b
	Residual	9055,711	175	51,747		
	Total	10422,254	180			
a. Dependent Variable: NIATREKOMENDASI						
b. Predictors: (Constant), SARANA, MATERI, MANFAAT, FASILITAS, TRAINER						

Based on the table above, it can be interpreted: The calculated F value is 5.282 with regression degrees of freedom (df) = 5 and residual df = 175. The Sig. (p-value) is <0.001, which is much smaller than the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Because Sig. (0.001) < 0.05, then H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted. This means that together the five independent variables, Perception of Training Material (X1), Perception of Benefits (X2), Perception of Trainer (X3), Perception of Facilities (X4), and Perception of Facilities (X5)—have a significant effect on the dependent variable Recommendation Intention (Y1). The significant F test results (Sig. <0.001) indicate that the regression model formed is suitable for predicting Recommendation Intention based on the five perception factors. Although previously the coefficient of determination (R Square) showed a non-dominant contribution (13.1%), the significance of the F test confirmed that the existing influence was statistically real. This aligns with the theoretical framework that states that participants' perceptions of various aspects of training delivery, such as materials, benefits, trainers, facilities, and resources, can shape their intention to recommend the training to others. Practical implications: Training providers can use this model as a basis for holistically improving training quality, although it is important to remember that other factors outside the model also play a role. The significance of the F-test also provides support for further analysis to the partial test stage (t-test) to determine which variables exert the most dominant influence. Thus, these findings not only confirm the model's feasibility but also open

up space for more in-depth testing of the contribution of each independent variable. The hypothesis tested for each variable is: **H₀**: There is no significant influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. **H₁**: There is a significant influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The significance level used is $\alpha = 0.05$. The decision is taken by comparing the **Sig. value** with α : If **Sig. < 0.05**, then **H₀** is rejected (the variable has a significant effect). If **Sig. \geq 0.05**, then **H₀** fails to be rejected (the variable has no significant effect).

The results of data processing with SPSS version 29 produce the following regression coefficient output:

Table 8. t-Test Results

Model		Coefficients ^a		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error			
Niat Rekomendasi	(Constant)	7,562	5,851		1,292	0,198
	MATERI	0,021	0,046	0,036	0,460	0,646
	MANFAAT	-1,647	0,336	-1,029	-4,905	0,000
	TRAINER	1,469	0,350	0,892	4,193	0,000
	FASILITAS	-0,204	0,261	-0,116	-0,781	0,436
	SARANA	0,316	0,256	0,185	1,232	0,219

a. Dependent Variable: NIATREKOMENDASI

Based on the table above, it can be interpreted as follows: 1) Constant = 7.562 with a Sig. value of 0.198 (> 0.05). This shows that if all independent variables are considered zero, then the Recommendation Intention is not significantly different from zero. An insignificant constant value is normal in the context of this study. 2) Training Material (X1) has a regression coefficient B = 0.021 and Sig. = 0.646 (> 0.05). Thus, **H₀** fails to be rejected, meaning that Training Material does not have a significant effect on Recommendation Intention. 3) Benefits (X2) have directional regression coefficient. With Sig. < 0.05 , **H₀** is rejected, meaning that Benefits have a significant negative effect B = -1.647 and Sig. = 0.000 (< 0.05). A negative coefficient value indicates an inverse relationship to Recommendation Intention. Each unit increase in perceived benefits actually decreases recommendation intention by 1.647 units, assuming other variables remain constant. 4) Trainer (X3) has a regression coefficient B = 1.469 and Sig. = 0.000 (< 0.05). With Sig. < 0.05 , **H₀** is rejected, meaning that Trainer has a significant positive effect on Recommendation Intention. Each unit increase in perception towards trainers will increase recommendation intention by 1.469 units, assuming other variables remain constant. 5) Facility (X4) has regression coefficient B = -0.204 and Sig. = 0.436 (> 0.05).

Thus, **H₀** fails to be rejected, meaning that Facility does not have a significant effect on Recommendation Intention. Facility (X5) has a regression coefficient B = 0.316 and Sig. = 0.219 (> 0.05). Thus, **H₀** fails to be rejected, meaning that Facility Perception does not have a significant effect on Recommendation Intention. Based on the partial test, only two variables significantly influence Recommendation Intention, namely Perceived Benefits (X2) and Trainer Perception (X3). Meanwhile, Perception of Training Material, Perception of Facilities, and Perception of Facilities did not show a significant influence. An interesting result is the discovery of a significant negative influence of Perceived Benefits. This phenomenon can be explained by several possibilities, for example: The effect of unmet expectations: Participants who have a high perception of the benefits of the training may also have high expectations, so that if these expectations are not fully realized, it can actually reduce their intention to recommend. Moderating or mediating factors: There may be other variables that moderate the relationship between perceived benefits and recommendation intention, such as overall satisfaction or the quality of post-training implementation. On the other hand, the Trainer has a significant positive effect, indicating that the trainer's competence, skills, and delivery method are key factors that encourage participants to recommend the training to others. This is in line with many studies that emphasize the central role of trainers in training effectiveness. Other insignificant variables may be due to: Redundancy factors: Dimensions such as facilities and resources may already be included in perceptions of trainers or benefits, so their unique contribution is small. Research context: In certain training courses, aspects of materials, facilities, and resources may be considered as minimum standards that must be present, so they do not become differentiators in forming recommendation intentions. The practical implication of this finding is that training organizers need to focus on improving the quality of trainers and managing participants'

expectations regarding training benefits realistically. Meanwhile, the quality of aspects of materials, facilities, and resources still needs to be maintained as part of the standards for professional training delivery.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis results above, several important findings can be discussed: Significant simultaneous influence – Although the contribution of the five variables is relatively small (13.1%), their influence is statistically significant. This indicates that the five aspects of perception still play a role in shaping Recommendation Intention, although not dominant. Different partial influence – Of the five variables, only Perception Benefits and Trainer Perceptions have a significant influence. Interestingly, Perceived Benefits showed a negative influence, which may be caused by participants' overly high expectations of the training's benefits, which, if not met, would actually reduce their recommendation intentions. The key role of the Trainer – This result is in line with the theory that trainer quality is a major determinant of training effectiveness. The trainer's competence and ability to deliver the material turned out to be more influential than the material itself. Insignificant variables – The insignificance of Perceived Materials, Facilities, and Facilities may be due to: These factors are considered minimum standards that must be met. Their influence is indirect on recommendation intentions. There are other factors that are more dominant in the context of this study

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All authors contributed equally to this research and approved the final version of the manuscript.

AI Usage Statement

The authors declare that artificial intelligence (AI)-assisted tools were used solely for language editing and grammar improvement purposes. AI tools were not used for data analysis, interpretation of results, or generation of research findings. All analytical procedures and conclusions presented in this study were conducted and verified by the authors.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article.

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